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The Use of New Halal Labeling for Snack Food Production (The Chips by Zkiyah) in Banda Aceh

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Abstract

Written in Halal labeling is a label that informs consumers that the product is halal and the ingredients it contains do not contain prohibited elements so that the product can be consumed by consumers. Product packaging that contains a halal label makes it easier for consumers to identify a product that is halal. So, the aim of this research is to determine the use of new halal labeling in the production of The Chips by Zakiyah snack food in Banda Aceh. This research uses qualitative methods, and then the researcher carries out open interview techniques with research subjects and observations. The research results showed that consumers prefer products that use halal labels. And products that do not use the halal label have a big impact on consumers; besides that, consumers feel satisfied when they buy products that use the halal label. In conclusion, The Chips by Zakiyah is in the process of using the new halal labeling. And for consumers, the new halal label has no effect on purchasing the product.

Keyword: Labeling; Halal; Product; Aceh; Chips

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Received 24 January 2024; Received in revised form 23 February 2024; Accepted 1 April 2024; Available online 04 May 2024

<https://doi.org/>

Page 120-130

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INTRODUCTION

When consumers buy a product, they will choose carefully the product because, in decision-making, consumers will try to dig up information about how they will make the right purchase decision. Which causes consumers to think critically when finding information about the product to be used. (Alfian & Marpaung, 2017; Rahman, 2023). In Indonesia, there is a government that is specifically tasked with auditing products that will be consumed by consumers, especially Muslims in Indonesia. This is the Lembaga Pengawasan dan Peredaran Obat dan Makanan Majelis Ulama Indonesia (LPOMMUI), which aims to supervise products circulating in the community by providing halal certificates, with the intention that the product has been processed and has passed because the content does not contain elements that are forbidden and prohibited by Islam so that it can be consumed halal. (Syahputra & Hamoraon, 2014; Tiara, 2022).

The meaning of the word halal is to release and not be bound, so that it can be said epistemologically that halal is free and not bound by the provisions it prohibits. Halal has been written in the Quran, Surah Al-Baqarah, verse 168. (Wulandari, 2021; Misbah, 2019). The variety of labels is very diverse, ranging from simple product identification marks to complex graphics contained on product packaging. In addition, labels also inform things about the product, including who made it, where, when, contents, and how the product can be used and used safely. (Mukhtar & Nurif, 2015; Rudi, Wijaya, & Murdani, 2021).

Halal labeling is a label that provides information to consumers that the product is halal and the ingredients used do not contain elements that are haram in Sharia so that the product can be consumed by consumers (Bulan, 2016; Saputra & Irma, 2019; Paull, 2024). Halal labeling is a statement of halal, and the inclusion of writing with the aim of showing that the product is a halal product makes muslim consumers do not hesitate in consuming the products needed. (Wibowo & Mandusari, 2018; Munidar, 2024).

It will be easier for consumers to identify a product when the product packaging has a halal label. In Indonesia, products that have halal labels are very easy to find. So that products whose raw materials are not clear and whose processing could have been affixed with halal labels. However, the registration of halal labels has a requirement: it is mandatory to obtain halal certification from a special institution that will go through several tests on raw materials and manufacturing processes based on Islamic Sharia regulations. (Kamilah & Wahyuati, 2017; Cristina, 2024). In addition, halal labeling is not only a form of protection for the use of products that are halal or haram. Rather, it plays a role in avoiding fraud on a product. And halal certification is a must for a country to protect consumers from haram products. (Hamdani & Umuri, 2021; Ibrahi, 2024).

Based on the research background, it can be formulated that the problem of how the use of halal labeling affects the production of snacks The Chips by Zakiyah in Banda Aceh? with the aim of research to determine the use of new halal labeling in the production of snacks. the Chips by Zakiyah in Banda Aceh. The benefits of research provide information to the public that products that have been labeled halal can be purchased and used. And provide information to the public that Nahwa products that use the new halal logo have been used on Aceh products.

METHOD

The method used in this study is qualitative. The process of qualitative research involves an important effort, namely, asking questions and following procedures, collecting specific data,

analyzing the data inductively, interpreting the meaning of the data, and revealing the realistic conditions of the participants as the research, according to D. Creswell (2016).

As for the source of research data, Zakiyah produces the chips, as well as consumers. According to D. Creswell (2016), in qualitative research, we need to identify participation and place with purposeful sampling that is based on the places and people that help us the most in understanding our central phenomena.

The technique is an open interview with the subject of research and observation. The data collection tool used in this study is the interview. The data that has been obtained will be collected and analyzed using the qualitative descriptive method, namely inductive approach analysis. Qualitative data is in the form of an analytical statement or description of a statement in the form of an explanation by word or word, so that it will describe the meaning, description, clarification, and statement of data. Then analyze the word in the form of a research report. The data will be analyzed through data reduction, namely by classifying data based on existing problems, so that problems in the study can be answered precisely and accurately.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Results and discussion contain the results of research findings and scientific discussion. Write down the scientific findings obtained from the results of research that has been done, which must be supported by adequate data. The scientific findings referred to here are not only the data obtained from the research results. The scientific findings that should be explained scientifically include:

Interview with the owner.

1. When did this Zakiyah chips business start running?

Answer: beginning of business in 2010, spinach chips.

2. Why prefer to open a business by chips?

Answer: it used to be because I had a baby, so the stock of spinach was abundant because I was alone in the yard, I thought about making chips because I like to eat peanut chips, it turns out that the baby likes it and starts marketing, Alhamdulillah enthusiastic buyers like the spinach chips.

3. How much sales turnover of chips a day?

Answer: because selling system Made by order so can not be predicted how many days, except to join the bazaar is usually around 500,000 or more.

4. Do you find it difficult to open orders from home?

Answer: No, because it does not pursue the company's target.

5. What are the chips sold for?

Answer:

Spinach chips

Melinjo leaf chips

Temurui leaf chips

Wak asin banana chips

Sweet wak banana chips

Banana chips you catch
salted kepok chips
sweet kepok chips
kepok catch chips
original potato chips
potato chips balado
corn potato chips
potato chips catch
sambal goreng potato chips
garlic steak
purple yam steak
steak balado
corn sticks
green beans krenyes
onion tojin beans
Tojin beans catch
Savory manga seeds
Sweet manga seeds
Peanut paste
Mung bean paste
Peyek udang sabee
Do these zakiyah chips use halal logo?
Answer: true.

6. When was Zakiyah chips given Mui halal logo certificate?
Answer: halal permit from MPU Aceh issued on July 21, 2021.

7. What do you think about the transition from the old logo to the new one?
Answer: the problem of the new logo is now the renewal so that the halal logo in Indonesia is the same, and does not differ between each province in Indonesia, good for the diversity of Indonesia such as intellectual property patents, so even if there are in Java the product will not be the same name as the one in Aceh.
It can be concluded about the owner's opinion about the renewal of the old halal logo to the new one is the renewal of the new halal logo is good for the diversity of Indonesian.

8. Do you currently use the old halal logo or the new halal logo?
Answer: it's still the old one, the new logo is still in the management stage yet to come out, God willing, in the near future the wayang logo will come out, the old logo will still be valid until 2024
It can be concluded that the owner of the chips by Zakiyah is taking care of the renewal stage of the new halal logo.

9. If a new halal logo is established in Aceh, would you agree to use the new halal logo on zakiyah chips?

Answer: yes, I have taken care of the halal Ministry of religion, just wait for the permit to come out.

It can be concluded that the owner agreed to use the new halal logo on these Zakiyah chips.

10. Can the new halal logo affect Zakiyah's chips business?

Answer: God willing, it means that even though we Market on shopee or via other online, the chip's by zakiyah products are halal.

It can be concluded that with the new halal logo affects the business on this Zakiyah chips.

11. What do you think of the old logo and the new logo?

Answer: if the old logo is specifically for Acehese citizens, so if the people buy Medan, they know sometimes it's Aceh halal logo but if the Malaysian people buy sometimes they don't know it's Aceh halal, if the new logo is not only Indonesian people but even people outside other countries know because halal is issued by the state of Indonesia, each

It can be concluded that the owner's opinion about the old halal logo and the new halal logo is that the old halal logo is specifically for Acehese citizens while the new halal logo is the halal logo of Indonesia.

12. According to the mother, does this new halal logo have a negative or positive impact on food and beverage businesses?

Answer: obviously, because it has just been using halal country not province-specific

It can be concluded that the new halal logo has a positive impact on the food and beverage business.

13. How is the principle of using the halal logo on this Zakiyah chips business?

Answer: the principle if it is wearing a halal logo is not just a logo but consistent and consequent in the workmanship of the product, the use of halal raw materials is also.

It can be concluded that the principle of using the halal logo on zakiyahh chips is consistent, consequent, and the use of halal raw materials in the manufacture of products.

Interviews with consumers

1. Why choose products that use the halal logo?

Consumer 1: because the halal logo is guaranteed to be halal, it is hygienic, so it is given halal because it is guaranteed to be clean, It's guaranteed, so I choose halal for our needs, because if we are not halal, we cannot do anything, this halal product we can worship, worship halal, halal food, so we all become halal, if we are not halal we cannot, because we are native Muslims, Muslims choose halal products.

Consumer 2: because this halal logo is definitely halal in the use of raw materials, it is guaranteed that the use of the place is halal, it is halal standard, the process carried out is guaranteed by LPPOM MPU Aceh that this product is feasible to consume and halal.

Consumer 3: because it is guaranteed halal, it is more certain that we eat Muslims.

Consumer 4: if there is already a halal logo already in the label, it has been researched too, it is halal all the ingredients used are halal, we are Muslims.

It can be concluded that consumers prefer products that use the halal logo because it is guaranteed halal good place, raw materials, and has been guaranteed by Lppom Aceh that this product can be consumed.

2. What do you think if there is a product that does not use the halal logo?

Consumer 1: if suppose there is a product that uses halal not, we have no will, because we Muslims are recommended for halal if not halal, we do not have Muslims.

Consumer 2: Yes, Do not use the halal logo it is indeed if we In Aceh this we believe that we are Muslims, Muslims who Inshaallah definitely use it to use halal products because our environment is not contaminated with haram animals such as pigs, dogs and so on, but it is legally then we must do the product must be halal as well.

Consumers 3 and 4: if while selling we are sure he is a Muslim do not problem because of the product home Insha Allah sure, but if processed products such as meat doubt although Muslim appearance.

Can be concluded regarding consumer opinions about products that do not use the halal logo is that particularly in Aceh they believe that the products sold are worthy of consumption and produced in accordance with Islamic law unless the seller is a non-Muslim.

3. If there is a product that does not use the halal logo, will you still use it?

Consumer 1: no, if there is a halal logo I want to buy because there is already a guarantee, if there is we do not want to buy.

Consumer 2: yes, we still use it, because we live in an Islamic region, we believe that the Islamic community processes the product definitely by using halal products.

Consumers 3 and 4: if you know buy, but if do not know buy.

It can be concluded that products that do not use the halal is their logo are still using it da tone that is not, da tone also depends on knowing the seller.

4. Do food or drink products that are not halal logo have a big effect on you?

Konsumen1: yes, if there is a halal logo is not great influence for our Islamic religion.

Consumer 2: influence, if halal it believes that this is halal even though we say that this product is halal, I buy it, but I will choose the halal one First.

Consumers 3 and 4: highly influential

It can be concluded that food or beverage products that are not halal logo have a big effect on consumers.

5. What do you think about the transition from the old logo to the new one?

Consumer 1: if the old logo missal is replaced with a new one, we still check first what the goods are like, the products we process again to do halal in 2023.

Consumer 2: the new halal logo is more to the national network.

Consumers 3 and 4: like the Old, more clearly halal if the puppet is still in doubt. If this one is clearly the letter Ha, Lam

It can be concluded about consumer opinion about the renewal of the old halal logo to the new one is that there are consumers who claim that the renewal of the halal logo is

more to expand the national scale, but other consumers also state that even though the halal logo is done, they still check whether a product is halal or not.

6. What do you think of the products that have adopted the new halal logo?

Consumer 1: Alhamdulillah good, hygienic, guaranteed halal, the same as the old only more developed halal logo.

Consumer 2: nice and cooler logo, meaning that this product is already in national level.

Consumers 3 and 4: Normal, they must follow the rules of the name also we Indonesians must follow the rules of the government maybe they have started to follow the rules of the government, if the government rules so want to do not want, we have to wear the logo even though we do not like.

7. Does the new halal logo affect buying confidence?

Consumer 1: no influence, but we are checking better for the future.

Consumer 2: no influence, just the same in Aceh

Consumer 3: not too influential, same halal logo

Consumer 4: not too influential logo be different.

It can be concluded that the new halal logo has no effect on consumers in buying confidence.

8. How do you respond if there are two products whose prices are relatively different, products that have halal logos are more expensive and those that do not use halal logos are cheaper?

Consumer 1: I decided on the more expensive one because the expensive one is guaranteed halal.

Consumer 2: I prefer halal logo even though it is expensive.

Consumers 3 and 4: Choose What is halal even though it is expensive.

It can be concluded that consumers prefer products that have halal logos that are more expensive.

9. What are your principles in buying products that use halal logo?

Consumer 1: I feel proud, my spirit is more hygienic again.

Consumer 2: specifically, there is not that the product has been certified halal in content and so on then it will be more convincing in buying.

Consumers 3 and 4: no preservatives, flavoring

It can be concluded that the principle of consumers in buying products that use different halal logos is different.

10. Do you feel satisfied when buying food or beverage products with halal logos?

Consumer 1: yes, because it is very important halal logo for us.

Consumer 2: satisfied.

Consumers 3 and 4: Alhamdulillah satisfied so more confident if we eat if you want to be given to children so more confident.

It can be concluded that consumers are satisfied when buying food or beverage products with halal logos.

Figure 1. Interviews with consumers

Figure 2. observation

Based on the results of interviews, consumers prefer products that use the halal logo. This is in line with Windiana and Putri (2021) which state that products that use halal labels are foods that consumers want.

Furthermore, based on the interview results obtained that food or beverage products that are not labeled halal have a big effect on consumers. This is in line with (Wulandari, 2021) her research using multiple regression analysis which found that religiosity variables and halal labels are one of the main factors that affect consumers in buying indomie products in disidoarjo. Based on the interview results, label halal has a positive impact on the food and beverage business. This is in line with Nofianti and Rofiqoh (2019), who state that the persial test states the influence of awareness on halal labels. In the analysis of the influence of awareness and halal labels, it was positively proven to significantly affect the interest in buying.

Based on the results of interviews, consumers are satisfied when buying food or beverage products that have halal labels. This is in line with Sucipto, Nasiti P.A., Addina, & Septifani (2021) that the existence of halal labels and product quality affect the decision to purchase halal-certified tempeh chips that are not yet certified halal.

CONCLUSION

A Based on the results of research with the aim of determining the use of new halal labeling on the production of snacks called chips by Zakiyah in Banda Aceh, it can be concluded that the use

of new halal labeling on the chips by Zakiyah products is in the process of being done.

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